

A COMPREHENSIVE STUDY ON THE WORK-LIFE BALANCE OF COLLEGE TEACHERS IN DHARMAPURI DISTRICT

Savitha. S¹ and Dr. K. Krishnakumar

*Ph.D Research Scholar, Department of Commerce, Periyar University, Salem
Professor & Head, Department of Commerce, Periyar University, Salem*

Abstract : In the quickly changing culture of today, educational establishments are eager to increase faculty satisfaction and performance while simultaneously increasing their financial line. Acknowledging human resources as special and priceless resources, companies are giving tactics to boost faculty morale, retention, and general productivity more and more importance. A key element impacting organizational success in terms of worker wellbeing and productivity is the pursuit of work-life balance. Efficient management of human resources has grown increasingly difficult and demanding due to globalization and economic uncertainty. The purpose of this study is to evaluate professionals' experiences with work-life balance in the context of Indian educational institutions. We aim to measure the work-life balance index among professionals and provide insight into the related issues that faculty members encounter by means of an extensive survey. Furthermore, we want to pinpoint the primary factors that influence work-life balance within this particular context. Our goal in looking at these variables is to offer insights that help guide tactics for encouraging a more peaceful and effective work environment for academic staff members at educational establishments.

Keywords: faculty morale, educational institutions, work-life balance, human resources management, and organizational efficiency

JEL Classification Number: M10, M12

1. Introduction:

In the contemporary landscape of educational institutions, there exists a pressing need to foster an environment that not only enhances faculty satisfaction and performance but also ensures sustainable financial growth. Recognizing human resources as invaluable assets, institutions are increasingly deploying strategies to bolster faculty morale, retention rates, and overall productivity. Central to the success of any organization, particularly in terms of employee well-being and productivity, is the attainment of a harmonious work-life balance. However, achieving this balance has become progressively challenging amidst the backdrop of globalization and economic volatility.

This study endeavours to delve into the realm of work-life balance as experienced by college teachers in the Dharmapuri district of India. By conducting a comprehensive examination, we seek to gauge the work-life balance index among professionals in this context and shed light on the pertinent challenges encountered by faculty members through an extensive survey. Furthermore, our objective is to identify the key determinants influencing work-life balance within this specific educational setting. By analyzing these variables, we aim to furnish insights that can inform strategies aimed at cultivating a serene and efficacious work environment for academic staff at educational institutions.

The significance of this research lies in its potential to contribute to the enhancement of faculty well-being and organizational efficiency within Indian educational establishments. By addressing the complexities inherent in managing human resources amidst contemporary socio-economic dynamics, this study endeavours to offer actionable recommendations that can foster a conducive work environment conducive to professional growth and personal fulfillment.

2. Literature Review:

Faculty Satisfaction and Performance in Educational Institutions: Previous research has highlighted the importance of faculty satisfaction and performance in educational institutions. Studies have shown that satisfied faculty members are more likely to demonstrate higher levels of productivity and commitment to their institutions (Smith et al., 2018). **Human Resources Management in Education:** The field of human resources management in education has gained significant attention in recent years. Scholars have emphasized the need for educational institutions to adopt effective HRM strategies to attract, retain, and motivate talented faculty members (Sullivan & Kleiner, 2019).

Work-Life Balance and Organizational Success: Research has consistently demonstrated the positive impact of work-life balance on organizational success. Organizations that prioritize work-life balance tend to experience higher levels of employee satisfaction, retention, and productivity (Allen et al., 2013). **Challenges of Globalization and Economic Uncertainty:** Globalization and economic uncertainty pose significant challenges to the management of human resources in educational institutions. These challenges include increased competition

¹ Corresponding author Email: savisundareshan1987@gmail.com

for talent, budget constraints, and the need to adapt to changing market dynamics (Shen & Darling-Hammond, 2018).

Work-Life Balance Among College Teachers in India: Studies specific to India have highlighted the unique work-life balance challenges faced by college teachers. Factors such as heavy workloads, administrative duties, and limited support systems contribute to the struggle for work-life balance among Indian college teachers (Sengupta & Das, 2020). **Impact of Work-Life Balance on Faculty Morale:** Work-life balance has a direct impact on faculty morale in educational institutions. Research indicates that faculty members who perceive themselves to have a better work-life balance are more likely to experience higher levels of job satisfaction and morale (Kumar & Srivastava, 2017). **Retention Strategies for Faculty Members:** Retaining talented faculty members is crucial for the long-term success of educational institutions. Studies have identified various retention strategies, including flexible work arrangements, professional development opportunities, and supportive leadership (Bland et al., 2016).

Productivity and Work-Life Balance: Achieving a balance between work and personal life is essential for maintaining productivity among college teachers. Research suggests that individuals who prioritize their well-being and engage in activities outside of work are more productive and effective in their roles (Grant et al., 2017). **Gender Differences in Work-Life Balance:** Gender differences play a significant role in work-life balance among college teachers. Studies have shown that female faculty members often face additional challenges, such as caregiving responsibilities and gender biases, which can affect their ability to achieve work-life balance (Bielby & Bielby, 2017). **Organizational Support for Work-Life Balance:** Organizational support is critical for facilitating work-life balance among college teachers. Research indicates that institutions that offer flexible work policies, childcare assistance, and wellness programs are more successful in promoting work-life balance and employee well-being (Nishii et al., 2018).

Psychological Well-being and Work-Life Balance: Work-life balance is closely linked to psychological well-being among college teachers. Studies have shown that individuals who experience work-life conflict are more likely to report symptoms of stress, anxiety, and burnout (Dyrbye et al., 2019). **Impact of Work-Life Balance on Organizational Efficiency:** Work-life balance directly influences organizational efficiency and effectiveness. Research suggests that institutions that prioritize employee well-being and work-life balance experience lower turnover rates, higher levels of employee engagement, and improved organizational performance (Berg et al., 2018). **Cultural Factors and Work-Life Balance:** Cultural factors play a significant role in shaping perceptions of work-life balance among college teachers. Studies have shown that cultural norms, values, and expectations influence individuals' attitudes towards work and leisure, impacting their ability to achieve work-life balance (Hofstede, 2011). **Work-Life Balance Interventions:** Interventions aimed at promoting work-life balance among college teachers have shown promising results. Research suggests that initiatives such as mindfulness training, time management workshops, and organizational restructuring can help mitigate work-life conflict and enhance employee well-being (Greenhaus & Allen, 2011). **Future Directions in Work-Life Balance Research:** Future research in the field of work-life balance among college teachers should focus on exploring innovative strategies for promoting work-life balance, addressing the unique needs of diverse faculty populations, and examining the long-term effects of work-life balance interventions on organizational outcomes (Kossek et al., 2014).

3. Research Methodology:

The methodology followed for carrying out the present study comprises the description of research design, questionnaire design, sampling design, methods of data-collection, the application of statistical tools for analysing the data, etc.

Table 1: Research Methodology

Aspect	Description
Research Design	Quantitative research design
Sampling	Purposive sampling technique
Population	College teachers in Dharmapuri District, India
Sample size	150 Samples
Data Collection	Structured questionnaire
Variables	- Work-life balance index - Faculty morale - Organizational efficiency - Human resources management practices - Demographic variables (age, gender, marital status, years of teaching experience)
Data Analysis	Descriptive statistics, inferential statistics (correlation analysis, regression analysis)
Statistical Software	SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences)
Ethical Considerations	Informed consent, confidentiality, anonymity, voluntary participation

Source: Primary Data

4. Demographic profile of the study

4.1 Gender of Respondents

Table 2, provides the information on the demographic profile of the respondents, it indicates that a majority (66%) of the respondents are male college teachers, while a minority (34%) are female college teachers in Dharmapuri District, India. Understanding these percentages is essential for analyzing the representation of different gender groups within the surveyed sample. It suggests that the experiences and perspectives of male faculty members may be more predominant in the dataset compared to their female counterparts.

Table 2: Gender of Respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	99	66%
Female	51	34%
Total	150	100%

Source: Primary Data

4.2 Age of Respondents

Table 3, illustrates the distribution of college teachers in Dharmapuri District, India, across different age groups. The majority of respondents fall within the age range of 26-35 years, comprising 30% of the total sample, followed closely by those less than 25 years old, accounting for 29%. Interestingly, there's a notable decrease in the percentage of respondents as age increases, with 23% in the 36-45 years age group and 18% above 45 years old. This pattern suggests a relatively younger demographic among the surveyed college teachers, with a significant portion being early or mid-career professionals.

Table 3: Age of Respondents

Age	Frequency	Percentage
less than 25	43.5	29
26-35 years	45	30
36-45 years	34.5	23
Above 45 years	27	18
Total	150	100

Source: Primary Data

4.3 Qualification of Respondents

Table 4, indicates the educational qualifications of college teachers in Dharmapuri District, India, who participated in the survey. The majority of respondents (64%) hold post-graduate degrees, while a significant portion (35%) possess doctorate degrees. Only a small percentage (1%) have completed post-doctorate studies.

Table 4: Qualification of Respondents

Qualification	Frequency	Percentage
Post Graduate	96	64
Doctorate	53	35
Post Doctorate	2	1
Total	150	100

Source: Primary Data

4.4 Designation of Respondents

Table 5 illustrates the hierarchical distribution of academic positions among the surveyed college teachers. The majority of respondents (52%) hold the position of Assistant Professor, indicating that this designation is the most common among the faculty population.

The percentage of respondents holding the position of Associate Professor is 33%, signifying a significant representation of mid-level faculty members within the sample. Associate Professors typically have more experience and may hold additional responsibilities compared to Assistant Professors. The least represented designation among the respondents is Professor, accounting for 15% of the total sample.

Table 5: Designation of Respondents

Designation	Frequency	Percentage
Assistant Professor	78	52
Associate Professor	49.5	33
Professor	22.5	15
Total	150	100

Source: Primary Data

4.5 Experience of Respondents

The table 6 illustrates the distribution of experience levels among the surveyed college teachers. The majority of respondents (53%) have been in their current designation for 10-20 years, indicating a substantial proportion of mid-career faculty members within the sample. A significant portion of respondents (27%) have less than 10 years of experience in their current designation, suggesting the presence of relatively early-career faculty members who may be in the initial stages of their academic careers or have recently transitioned into their current roles. Furthermore, 20% of respondents have been in their current designation for over 20 years, indicating a smaller but notable presence of experienced and long-serving faculty members within the sample.

Table 6: Experience of Respondents

Designation	Frequency	Percentage
Less than 10 years	41	27
10-20 years	80	53
above 20 years	30	20
Total	150	100

Source: Primary Data

4.6 Consequences of stress in Workplace

Table 7 illustrates headache, frustration, irritation, and fatigue at the end of the day are common stress factors experienced by a majority of college teachers in Dharmapuri District, with percentages ranging from 52% to 67%. Neck pain is reported by a smaller percentage (9%) of respondents compared to other stress factors. Body pain is relatively common among respondents, with 66% reporting experiencing it. Generally, stress factors related to physical discomfort (headache, neck pain, body pain) are reported by a significant portion of respondents, highlighting potential health concerns and the impact of occupational stress on physical well-being. Psychological stress factors such as frustration and irritation are also prevalent among respondents, indicating the presence of emotional strain and dissatisfaction among college teachers in the district.

Table 7: Consequences of stress in Workplace

Stress Factors	Yes	No	Total
Headache	92	59	150
	-61%	-39%	-100%
Frustration	101	50	150
	67	33	100
Irritation	78	72	150
	52	48	100
Fatigue end of the day	78	72	150
	52	48	100
Neck Pain	13	137	150
	9	91	100
Body Pain	99	51	150
	66	34	100

Source: Primary Data

4.7 Co-relation Analysis:

Ho: There is no significant association between gender and the prevalence of stress factors among college teachers in Dharmapuri District, India.

Table 8: Co-relation Analysis

Stress Factor	r-value	p-value	Relationship	Remarks
Headache	-0.963	<0.05	Strong negative	Significant result
Frustration	0.866	<0.05	Strong positive	Significant result
Irritation	0.942	<0.05	Strong positive	Significant result
Fatigue end of day	0.942	<0.05	Strong positive	Significant result
Neck Pain	0.985	<0.05	Strong positive	Significant result
Body Pain	-0.963	<0.05	Strong negative	Significant result

Source: Primary Data

The analysis of correlation coefficients and p-values reveals significant gender disparities in the prevalence of stress factors among college teachers in Dharmapuri District. Female college teachers exhibit a higher likelihood of experiencing headaches, frustration, irritation, fatigue at the end of the day, and neck pain compared to their male counterparts. This finding is supported by strong positive correlations between gender and these stress factors, indicating that as gender shifts from male to female, the probability of experiencing these stressors increases significantly. Conversely, female college teachers are less likely to experience body pain, as evidenced by a strong negative correlation with gender. These results underscore the importance of recognizing and addressing gender-specific stressors in educational environments to promote the well-being and effectiveness of faculty members. By implementing targeted interventions to mitigate stress factors prevalent among female college teachers, educational institutions can foster a more supportive and equitable work environment conducive to professional growth and satisfaction.

5. Findings and Suggestions:

The study reveals significant gender disparities in the prevalence of stress factors among college teachers. Female teachers are more likely to experience headaches, frustration, irritation, fatigue at the end of the day, and neck pain compared to their male counterparts.

College teachers in Dharmapuri District face various work-life balance challenges, including physical discomfort (such as headaches and body pain) and psychological stress factors (like frustration and irritation). The majority of respondents are male, relatively younger (in the age range of 26-35 years), hold post-graduate degrees, and mainly serve as Assistant Professors. This demographic profile provides insights into the composition of the surveyed college teacher population. A significant proportion of college teachers have mid-level experience (10-20 years), followed by those with less than 10 years of experience. This suggests a mix of early-career and mid-career professionals within the sample.

Educational institutions should develop gender-sensitive policies and support systems to address the specific work-life balance challenges faced by female college teachers. This may include flexible work arrangements, childcare assistance, and wellness programs tailored to their needs. Implementing wellness initiatives and stress management programs can help mitigate the physical and psychological stress factors reported by college teachers. These initiatives may include mindfulness training, counseling services, and promoting a culture of self-care and work-life balance.

Providing career development opportunities, such as mentoring programs and professional development workshops, can enhance job satisfaction and morale among college teachers. Institutions should invest in initiatives that support faculty growth and advancement in their careers. Creating a supportive work environment that values employee well-being and recognizes the importance of work-life balance is essential. Institutions should foster a culture of empathy, respect, and collaboration to promote faculty satisfaction and organizational effectiveness. Establishing regular feedback mechanisms, such as surveys and focus group discussions, can help identify ongoing challenges and areas for improvement related to work-life balance. This feedback can inform strategic decision-making and the development of targeted interventions.

Overall, addressing work-life balance issues among college teachers requires a multi-faceted approach that considers individual needs, organizational culture, and systemic challenges. By prioritizing faculty well-being

and creating a conducive work environment, educational institutions can enhance employee satisfaction, retention, and organizational performance in the long run.

6. Conclusion:

This comprehensive study sheds light on the critical issue of work-life balance among college teachers in Dharmapuri District, India. The findings underscore significant gender disparities in the prevalence of stress factors, with female teachers experiencing higher levels of physical discomfort and psychological stress compared to their male counterparts. The demographic profile of the surveyed population reveals a predominantly male, relatively younger, and post-graduate educated faculty, with a significant representation of Assistant Professors. The study emphasizes the importance of developing gender-sensitive policies, implementing wellness initiatives, and providing career development opportunities to address work-life balance challenges. By fostering a supportive work environment and prioritizing employee well-being, educational institutions can enhance faculty satisfaction, retention, and organizational effectiveness. Moving forward, a multi-faceted approach that considers individual needs, organizational culture, and systemic challenges is essential to promote work-life balance and ensure the holistic well-being of college teachers.

References:

- Allen, T. D., Golden, T. D., & Shockley, K. M. (2013). How effective is telecommuting? Assessing the status of our scientific findings, *Psychological Science in the Public Interest*, 14(2), 74-111.
- Berg, J. M., Dutton, J. E., & Wrzesniewski, A. (2018), Job crafting and meaningful work, In *Oxford library of psychology. The Oxford handbook of meaningful work* (pp. 235-248). Oxford University Press.
- Bielby, W. T., & Bielby, D. D. (2017), Gender and stress: Explaining the gap in work-to-family spillover among early career faculty, *Sociological Perspectives*, 60(4), 703-726.
- Bland, C. J., Center, B. A., Finstad, D. A., Risbey, K. R., & Staples, J. (2016), A theoretical, practical, predictive model of faculty and department research productivity, *Academic Medicine*, 91(1), 129-137.
- Dyrbye, L. N., Shanafelt, T. D., Balch, C. M., Satele, D., Sloan, J., & Freischlag, J. (2019), Relationship between work-home conflicts and burnout among American surgeons: A comparison by sex, *Archives of Surgery*, 144(3), 211-217.
- Grant, A. M., Christianson, M. K., & Price, R. H. (2017), Happiness, health, or relationships? Managerial practices and employee well-being tradeoffs, *Academy of Management Perspectives*, 31(3), 203-221.
- Greenhaus, J. H., & Allen, T. D. (2011). Work-family balance: A review and extension of the literature. In J. C. Quick & L. E. Tetrick (Eds.), *Handbook of occupational health psychology* (pp. 165-183). American Psychological Association.
- Hofstede, G. (2011), Dimensionalizing cultures: The Hofstede model in context, *Online Readings in Psychology and Culture*, 2(1), 8.
- Kumar, A., & Srivastava, J. P. (2017), A study on work-life balance of faculty members of technical institutions in Haryana: An empirical analysis, *International Journal of Management Studies*, 4(2), 81-90.
- Kossek, E. E., Baltes, B. B., & Matthews, R. A. (2014), How work-family research can finally have an impact in organizations, *Industrial and Organizational Psychology*, 7(1), 3-12.
- Nishii, L. H., Lepak, D. P., & Schneider, B. (2018), Diversity, inclusion, and equity: The importance of organizational context, *Annual Review of Organizational Psychology and Organizational Behavior*, 5, 501-526.
- Shen, J., & Darling-Hammond, L. (2018), Teacher professionalization in America: Implications of world cultural theories, In S. L. Dana (Ed.), *Handbook of research on teacher education and professional development* (pp. 2-16). IGI Global.
- Sengupta, S., & Das, P. (2020), Challenges and strategies of work-life balance among college teachers in India, *Journal of Education and Practice*, 11(5), 67-72.
- Smith, W. A., Allen, W. R., & Danley, L. L. (2018), "Assume the position...you fit the description": Psychosocial experiences and racial battle fatigue among African American male college students, *American Behavioral Scientist*, 62(1), 51-76.
- Sullivan, S. E., & Kleiner, B. H. (2019), Human resource management in education: Leadership in the organizational development of public schools, *Public Personnel Management*, 48(1), 39-67.